

WIRELESS NETWORK THROUGHPUT MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the current technological environment, real-time access to the Internet is becoming as important as access to a desktop computer was a decade ago. As cellular and PCS phones become more ubiquitous, the availability of mobile voice communications leads to a natural desire for mobile Internet access. This report details throughput studies performed on five different wireless data access technologies. These include one purely cellular technology, cellular digital packet data, which is carried on AMPS channels, and two PCS technologies, IS-95 and GSM. In addition a wireless mobile computing device (PDA) is examined, as well as a proprietary microcellular system.

All five technologies were tested in stationary modes and the cellular/PCS based systems were also tested in a mobile configuration at highway speeds. This study involved the use of the FTP service to investigate throughput at a user level as well as a study of packet by packet transfers. Measurements of a line modem are also given for comparison.

INTRODUCTION

The radio and computing hardware, in conjunction with the software protocols that make data communication possible, create a multi-dimensional environment. The widespread availability of Personal Communications Service (PCS) /cellular telephones makes this the predominant technology for wireless network access, particularly in times of national emergency. Wireless network access can insure the uninterrupted service of many Government agencies under emergency conditions. From the federal user's point of view, the most salient network parameter is often throughput.

In general, wireless network measurements are complex because of the inability to access the intermediate linkages of the communications circuit. Although these portions of the circuit remain invisible to the user, this inaccessibility does not adversely affect end-to-end throughput measurements.

This paper presents the results of experiments performed to verify the data throughput of five different wireless

networking technologies. It begins with a short description of each technology, followed by anecdotal notes concerning implementation of data service on each of these technologies. Finally, results of throughput measurements are presented.

WIRELESS DATA TECHNOLOGIES

Each of the technologies discussed in this paper has a theoretical maximum data throughput rate which is determined by factors such as the raw bit rate of the modulation scheme, whether data packets are repetitively transmitted according to the standard, the inclusion of error correcting codes, and the allowable bandwidth of a channel. On any digital network, including wireless networks, this theoretical maximum rate will be reduced by the occurrence of packet collisions, packet retransmissions, protocol overhead and other phenomena. These effects cause all digital networks to achieve throughput rates that are less than their maximum theoretical values.

Cellular digital packet data is deployed over the Advanced Mobile Phone Service (AMPS). The AMPS network carries both packetized data and regular voice traffic. Cellular digital packet data uses the same frequencies and bandwidth as AMPS, 30 kHz channels in the 800 MHz cellular band, with a theoretical data rate of 19.2 kbps. Unfortunately, AMPS coverage does not necessarily imply cellular digital packet data coverage, since a cellular digital packet data compatible modem must exist within each AMPS cell. Cellular digital packet data compatible data modem service has not been implemented widely and must be tested on a case by case basis.

In the U.S., Global System for Mobile communications (GSM) operates in the 1900 MHz PCS band but European GSM utilizes the 1800 MHz and 900 MHz bands. The channel bandwidth is 200 kHz, where each channel represents 8 time slots. The theoretical data transfer rate of a GSM network is 9600 bits per second.

IS-95 uses a pseudo-random code to spread a baseband signal over a 1.25 MHz bandwidth. This system allows many users to exist in the same spectral bandwidth simultaneously. IS-95 operates in the 800 and 1900 MHz bands. The

theoretical data throughput is 14.4 kbps. IS-95 is the basis for third generation wireless technologies.

One PDA incorporates a wireless modem into its design. The wireless network used in this system operates in the 900 MHz Specialized Mobile Radio (SMR) band. The underlying proprietary protocol supports TCP/IP at a theoretical rate of 8 kbps, half-duplex.

Another available technology incorporating a microcellular wireless network uses transceivers mounted on streetlights or utility poles to realize its frequency hopping spread spectrum system. The modems communicate over the 900 MHz Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) band, and the transceivers communicate with each other over both the 900 and 2.4 MHz ISM bands. This service has a theoretical maximum rate of 128 kbps and is available in selected urban areas of 36 states.

These 5 systems (IS-95, GSM, cellular digital packet data, wireless PDA and microcellular wireless) were tested to determine gross throughput during a typical stationary remote FTP session. The cellular and PCS technologies also were tested in a mobile configuration at highway speeds.

WIRELESS SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

IS-95 and GSM phones can be used as wireless data modems. However, connecting a phone to a mobile computing platform takes a few more steps than connecting a modem to a RJ-11 line socket. Both phones in this test required software drivers that emulate line modem functionality.

The IS-95 phone used in these tests incorporated a modem that required only the installation of a relatively simple driver. In contrast to the GSM phone, IS-95 did not require an additional data service plan.

The lack of a common standard for connections between laptops and wireless networking devices poses another set of difficulties. Connectors vary from manufacturer to manufacturer and even within a single manufacturer's family of phones multiple cable types are used. Care must be exercised to assure that compatible cables and drivers are obtained.

The cellular digital packet data device, in contrast to the PCS phone modems, was implemented as a PDA external accessory. The control software, modem and wireless service were acquired from a single vendor as a package. This single

vendor also supplied technical support for all software and hardware issues.

This situation is similar in the case of the wireless modem integrated PDA. Although the wireless service is a separate purchase, the PDA powers up as soon as the antenna is raised and no further setup is required.

The microcellular wireless modem requires the installation of a specialized driver in the computer. Support is handled by a third party Internet service provider. This system has limited coverage and market penetration, so hardware compatibility issues may arise. The modem proved incompatible with the computing platform used in the PCS/cellular tests, so an alternate platform was used

TEST METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

In the series of experiments that follow, care was taken to eliminate as much of the intermediate network as possible. Toward that end, an independent Point-to-Point Protocol (PPP) Linux server was configured to accept wireless IP data service requests, which represented the stationary end of the connection. The mobile end of the connection was implemented through the use of several different computing platforms and five wireless modems. For completeness, and to provide a baseline for comparison, measurements of a wired modem connection also were conducted.

Tests were conducted during normal working hours with no regard for 'busy hours'. Results represent an ensemble of tests conducted during different portions of a work day so that network variations are included but not emphasized. Each technology was tested multiple times. All results represent complete file transfers - results from partial transfers were discarded.

The experiments involved two different levels of testing. In the user level tests, test files containing random byte sequences were transmitted from an FTP server on the Linux machine to the mobile and the time reported by the FTP software was used to calculate the throughput rate on a file by file basis. Random byte files guard against any potential compression in the modem implementations. Differing file sizes were used to examine their relationship to throughput.

A more meticulous examination of the fine structure of these data transfers requires packet level information. Packet level information gives a view of the instantaneous throughput during a file transfer session as well as indicating the characteristics of the individual packets transmitted.

The results of user level tests are shown in Table 1. Calculated values of the standard deviation and 95% confidence interval are given for each technology and file size. Each of the entries in Table 1 represents the results of approximately 50 experiments conducted with the associated technology.

Medium	Mode	File Size (kB)	Throughput (kbps)	Std. Dev. (kbps)	95% Confidence Interval (kbps)
Cellular Digital Packet Data	Mobile	10	1.5*	0.54	0.33
	Stationary	10	2.1*	0.20	0.11
		100	2.1*	0.15	0.09
IS-95	Mobile	10	8.4	0.87	0.30
		100	10.7	0.47	0.17
	Stationary	10	8.7	1.14	0.41
		100	11.3	0.23	0.10
GSM	Mobile	10	7.0	0.62	0.21
		100	7.9	0.39	0.14
	Stationary	10	7.3	0.04	0.01
		100	8.5	0.00	0.00
Wireless PDA	Stationary	10	1.4*	0.01	0.01
		100	1.4*	0.01	0.01
Microcell	Stationary	10	44.4	15.60	4.83
		100	97.8	27.43	8.50
9.6 kbps Line Modem	Stationary	mixed	7.2	0.72	0.32

*It should be noted that the two technologies that showed the lowest percentages of their theoretical rates, cellular digital packet data and wireless PDA, were tested using PDAs because of hardware restrictions. The relatively slow processors and serial port speeds may have negatively biased the results.

Table 1. Throughputs for wireless data networks

The PCS based data transport technologies, IS-95 and GSM, show very little variation in throughput rate between their mobile and stationary configurations. This is indicative of the high quality of the equalization networks within these technologies and implies that they are excellent choices for mobile modes. Both show similar throughput rates so that available coverage is probably the overriding factor in deciding between these two technologies.

The newest and fastest technology is the microcellular system, which had measured throughputs approximately five to ten times those of the PCS technologies. The small file

throughput measured for this system was considerably less than that measured for the large files. The reasons for this effect are not evident from measurements at this granularity and packet level investigations are needed.

It is not surprising that none of these technologies achieves its theoretical rate. For example, the line modem achieved only 75% of its theoretical rate. This indicates that protocol overhead can significantly reduce measured throughput, even in tightly controlled communications channels like the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN).

As expected, mobile throughput rates are somewhat smaller than those of the stationary configuration. However, the large difference between rates for smaller versus larger files was surprising. This is probably due to significant startup periods contributing to the time required for file transfer.

An investigation at the packet level is shown in Figure 1 which shows the result of a 100 kB file transfer over a IS-95 channel to a stationary client. As the graph shows, after 15 kilobytes are transferred the data rate becomes constant demonstrating that the channel is robust in this experiment, since retransmissions would cause portions of the graph to show a diminished slope indicating a lower throughput.

Figure 1. IS-95 100 kB File Transfer

During the early portion of the file transmission, before 15 kilobytes are transferred, the graph indicates an exponential characteristic. This is due to the ‘slow start’ algorithm implicit in TCP.

A closer examination of the first 10 kilobytes transferred, given in Figure 2, shows that there is significant variation in the slope of the graph (and therefore the throughput). However, this graph indicates that the throughput rate for the early portion of the file transfer is higher than the average throughput. This contradicts the results in the Table and may indicate that the FTP setup times can negatively skew

Figure 2. Detail of IS-95 100 kB File Transfer

throughput measurements. This effect would be expected to be more prominent on smaller file transfers.

CONCLUSIONS

These experiments indicate that currently available PCS technologies offer robust data transmission at actual rates of about 8 kbps. These technologies have well-implemented equalization capabilities which allow them to be used in mobile modes at highway speeds. It should be noted that these experiments do not address connection latency.

Transport systems operating at cellular frequencies exhibited lower throughput rates in these experiments, but this may have been due to characteristics of the mobile computing platform used. However, carrier frequency apparently is not a factor. The microcellular system, which operates at similar frequencies, offers significantly higher throughput rates than those of the PCS systems.

Packet level measurements indicate that current FTP algorithms place a penalty on small file transfers. This behavior in all likelihood will prove detrimental to file transfers where deep fade channel impairments become an issue.

There is a great deal of interest within the Internet community in the effect of base station handoff on wireless data transfer. This has impact at several different scales. Future work utilizing the packet level measurements developed here, correlated with handoff event timing, will be used to examine this mechanism.